

Dual Arrangement, Elastic Scattering-Uniform Distribution Statistical Approaches Applied to the Kaniadakis Distribution

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In a previous note (1), we argued that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, there seems to be a dual situation in that one may solve for the distribution from a local subset $e_i + e_j = E_1$ constant using a uniform distribution, i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E_1$ and find $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ (i.e. physical elastic scattering), or use a global approach. The global approach is also physical in that it maximizes the number of arrangements $N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$ where $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$ subject to $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. Thus, the constraint applies to the global approach and not to the local. The local approach is automatically an approximation because for $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$ (unnormalized) $e_i = 0.8 E_{\text{total}}$ and $e_j = 0.7 E_{\text{total}}$ are physical, but $1.5 E_{\text{total}}$ is not, but is accommodated by $C \exp(-e_i/T)$. On the other hand, the global arrangement approach is exact, but if one uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$, it is consistent with the local approach.

In Part 1, we considered the Tsallis case by using the global constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$ power $q = \text{number}$. When focusing on the local approach, which does not use the global constraint, we found that there were at least two solutions, namely $p(e_i)_{\text{Tsallis}} = (1 + (1-q)x)^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$ where $x = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)_{\text{Kaniadakis}} = (\sqrt{1 + (1-q)(1-q)x^2} + (1-q)x)^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$. In the local approach we were not able to pick one or the other and so we considered the global one. We argued that in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit, the entropy expression should reduce to the arrangement result using Stirling's approximation, i.e. $-p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. We thus considered $p(e_i)^{\text{power } q} F(q, p(e_i))$ as our entropy expression, in keeping with the global constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)^{\text{power } q}$ and noted that the global approach picks between the two solutions found in the local approach.

Here we argue that it is because the local approach does not use a global constraint that one has the two math solutions $p(e_i)_{\text{Tsallis}}$ and $p(e_i)_{\text{Kaniadakis}}$ which both become $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit. The only reason the constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)^{\text{power } q}$ picks out the Tsallis solution is that one fashions the entropy using $p(e_i)^{\text{power } q} F(\text{Tsallis})(q, p(e_i))$ such that $F(q, p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. One may actually create a second global constraint, $\text{Sum over } i p(e_i) e_i$ and then fashion $p(e_i) F(\text{Kaniadakis})$ such that $p(e_i)_{\text{Kaniadakis}}$ solution is picked from the local two function set. In particular, $d/dp \{ p^{\text{power } q} (1 - p^{\text{power } (1-q)}) / (1-q) = -e_i/T + 1$ in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit for the Tsallis case, and $d/dp \{ p (p^{\text{power } (1-q)} - p^{\text{power } -(1-q)}) / (2(1-q))$ in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit also yields the same result. Thus, it does seem that there is a dualism present. The local approach yields two possible solutions as it is not associated with any global constraint, but then linking to a global approach, one constraint $\text{Sum over } i p(e_i)^{\text{power } q} e_i$ picks out the $p(e_i)_{\text{Tsallis}}$, while $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$ picks out $p(e_i)_{\text{Kaniadakis}}$.

Dual Approach

We argued in (1) that a dual physical approach seems to exist in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. Both approaches are based on physical scenarios. The first considers a subset, namely $e_i + e_j =$

E_1 , where E_1 is a constant. Then $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l = E_1$. This leads to $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ in general. One may even create a Shannon's entropy expression such that this math function when maximized (d/dp) subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$ yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. At first it appears that the subset-uniform distribution approach is the more general, but in Part 1 we argued this is not the case.

There exists an independent global, physical approach to solving the problem, i.e. maximizing the number of arrangements:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)! \quad \text{where } n(e_i) = N p(e_i) \quad ((1))$$

subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{ave}}$. ((2)) ((1)),((2)) are exact expressions, no approximation is used in the global approach, but the local subset approach is based on an approximation because:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j) \quad \text{for } p \text{ unnormalized } ((3)) \text{ means that:}$$

$e_i = .8 E_{\text{total}}$ and $e_j = .7 E_{\text{total}}$ yield $e_i+e_j = 1.5 E_{\text{total}}$ which is unphysical, but is handled by $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ which matches experiment.

For the global approach to match the local, one must use Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, there are two independent physical approaches, one global and one local.

Tsallis Case

In (1), we applied the above reasoning to the Tsallis case. We argued that the Tsallis case is based on the global constraint:

$$\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = \text{number} \quad ((5))$$

The local approach, however, does not use any global constraint ((5)) and so we found two functions:

$$p(e_i)_{\text{Tsallis}} = (1 + (1-q)x)^{1/(1-q)} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((6a)) \text{ and}$$

$$p(e_i)_{\text{Kaniadakis}} = (\sqrt{1 + (1-q)(1-q)xx} + (1-q)x)^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((6b))$$

Both ((6a)) and ((6b)) become $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $q \rightarrow 1$, so one does not know which one to choose.

To resolve this issue in (1), we argued that one must have an entropy expression which in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit becomes the global arrangement result with Stirling's approximation. Given that we chose the constraint ((5)), we fashioned the entropy as:

$$- \sum_i p(e_i) \ln p(e_i) \quad (7)$$

In other words, we used the form $p(e_i) \ln p(e_i)$ which is linked with the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. This allowed us to pick out the $p(e_i)$ Tsallis from the local approach through:

$$\frac{d}{dp} (p \ln p) = -\frac{1}{p} + 1 \quad \text{for } p \rightarrow 1 \text{ and } F(q,p) = \frac{1}{(1-q)} (1 - p^{1-q}) \quad (8)$$

((8)) is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$ Tsallis.

In (1) we argued that the global approach allowed one to pick one of the two solutions from the local subset solution set. This, however, seems to occur because one uses a specific global constraint in the global approach. In other words, the constraint ((5)) picks out $p(e_i)$ Tsallis.

Kaniadakis Case

The local subset case does not use a global constraint so we argue that:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = \text{number} \quad (9)$$

is a perfectly fine global constraint and one is not forced to use ((5)). Using ((5)) in an entropy expression picks out a matching function $p(e_i)$ Tsallis from the two subset solutions. Then ((9)) should pick out $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis. To see this consider:

$$\frac{d}{dp} \left\{ \frac{1}{2(1-q)} (p^{1-q} - p^{-(1-q)}) \right\} = -\frac{1}{p} + p^{1-q} + p^{-(1-q)} \quad (10)$$

For $q \rightarrow 1$, one again obtains $-\frac{1}{p} + 1$, but this time one has used $F_{\text{Kaniadakis}} = \frac{1}{2(1-q)} (p^{1-q} - p^{-(1-q)})$ which is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis.

The global and local approaches still apply (there is dualism), but the global constraint used in the global approach picks out a function from the local approach. The local approach does not use any global constraint and so has at least two functions which become $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in (1) that there exist two independent physical approaches to solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. One is global and uses maximization of physical arrangements subject to the global constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, while the other is local and does not use a constraint, but rather employs a uniform distribution for the product distribution. $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as long as $e_i + e_j = E = \text{constant}$.

We then tried to apply these ideas to the Tsallis distribution, but chose a specific global constraint: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln p(e_i)$. The local approach does not use any global constraint and so at least two solutions emerged, $p(e_i)$ Tsallis and $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis such that each

becomes $\exp(-e_i/T)$ when $q \rightarrow 1$. Without a global constraint, one cannot select between one or the other in the local case. In the global case, however, the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ picks out $p(e_i)$ Tsallis, while the global constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ picks out the Kaniadakis solution. For the Tsallis case: $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dp} (p^{1/(1-q)} (1 - p^{1/(1-q)})) = -e_i/T + 1$, and for the Kaniadakis case, $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dp} (p^{1/(2(1-q))} (p^{1/(1-q)} - p^{-1/(1-q)})) = -e_i/T + 1$ as well. Thus, dualism seems to be present.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Dual Arrangement, Elastic Scattering-Uniform Distribution Statistical Approaches Applied to the Kaniadakis Distribution (preprint, zenodo, 2025)